

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF LAPAROSCOPY IN THE TREATMENT OF EARLY ENDOMETRIAL CANCER AND ITS IMPACT ON PATIENTS' SEXUAL FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to rigorously assess the clinical efficacy of laparoscopic surgery as compared to traditional laparotomy for the treatment of early-stage endometrial cancer, with a specialized focus on its subsequent impact on patients' sexual functionality. A retrospective analysis was executed, involving 76 patients diagnosed with early-stage endometrial cancer and treated at our institution between February 2021 and February 2022. Patients were bifurcated into two cohorts: one subjected to laparotomy (n=38), and the other to laparoscopic surgery (n=38). The study undertook a comprehensive analysis of perioperative metrics, postoperative complications, and both pre- and postoperative evaluations of sexual function, nutritional markers (serum total protein [TP], albumin [ALB], and prealbumin [PAB]), and inflammatory indices (C-reactive protein [CRP], tumor necrosis factor- α [TNF- α], and interleukin-6 [IL-6]). Laparoscopic intervention manifested a statistically significant reduction in operative duration, intraoperative hemorrhage, time to postoperative flatus, and overall hospitalization period compared to the laparotomy group ($P < 0.05$). The quantity of lymph nodes excised was statistically equivalent between the two modalities ($P > 0.05$). Sexual function parameters remained relatively stable postoperatively in the

laparoscopic cohort, in stark contrast to a notable decline in the laparotomy group ($P < 0.05$). Additionally, the laparoscopic approach demonstrated superior postoperative nutritional and inflammatory profiles ($P < 0.05$) and a markedly lower complication incidence of 13.16% vis-à-vis 34.19% in the laparotomy arm ($P < 0.05$). Laparoscopic surgery emerges as a less invasive yet equally efficacious modality for the treatment of early-stage endometrial cancer, delivering comparable lymphadenectomy outcomes to laparotomy. The approach not only mitigates the rate of postoperative complications but also exerts a preservative effect on sexual function and engenders a more favorable postoperative inflammatory and nutritional milieu.

[Key words] Laparoscope; Early endometrial cancer; Clinical efficacy; Sexual function

INTRODUCTION

Endometrial cancer is a common malignant tumor in gynecology, mostly in perimenopausal and postmenopausal women, and uterine bleeding is its main clinical symptom^[1-2]. Dysfunction of lipid metabolism, diabetes, hypertension, and obesity can all be important factors in inducing endometrial cancer, but the specific mechanism has not been fully revealed^[3-4]. Recently, the incidence of endometrial carcinoma in the world showed a obvious increase trend, and the mortality rate is relatively high. It has become a malignant tumor that threatens women's life and health^[5-6]. Therefore, early diagnosis and timely and effective standardized treatment are important means to improve the survival rate of endometrial carcinoma sufferers. Surgery is the most effective way to treat sufferers with early endometrial cancer, the treatment effects are definite, and the 5-year survival ratio after surgery exceeds 70%^[7-8]. However, traditional laparotomy can bring greater trauma to patients, and the amount of blood loss during the surgery is large, which prolongs the recovery time of the patients, and the risk of sexual dysfunction is greater; in addition, some patients with weaker constitutions cannot tolerate surgery, which limits the scope of traditional laparotomy to a certain extent^[9-11]. In recent years, minimally invasive technology has made a great progress. Laparoscopic surgery has gradually been widely used in clinical treatment that can reduce the degree of body trauma, reduce intraoperative blood loss, and lighten the stress response. It has a vital function in reducing the risk of complications and improving the quality of life after surgery^[12-13]. However, there is still some controversy about the efficacy in clinic of laparoscopic operation in the therapy of endometrial carcinoma at this stage. Based on the above background, this study aims to explore the efficacy in clinic of laparoscopic operation in the therapy of early endometrial carcinoma and its impact on the sexual function of sufferers, to give a reference for clinical guidance in the therapy of endometrial carcinoma.

METHODOLOGY

Normal data

The clinical data of 76 sufferers with endometrial carcinoma who were received in our hospital between February 2021 and February 2022 were collected and made retrospective analysis. Based on different treatment ways, sufferers were divided into a laparotomy one and a laparoscopy one, each with 38 patients with endometrial

cancer. The laparotomy one had a mean age of (42.66±7.25) years, a mean disease duration of (1.67±0.39) years, and for the FIGO staging, there were 22 instances of stage Ia, and 16 instances of stage Ib; the laparoscopy one had a mean age of (42.83±7.13) years, a mean illness duration of (1.63±0.42) years, and for the FIGO staging, there were 21 instances of stage Ia, and 17 instances of stage Ib. It had no obvious distinction in the baseline data between the 2 groups after statistical software testing ($P > 0.05$). See Table 1.

Table 1 Baseline data

Group	n	Age (Years)	Course of disease (Years)	of FIGO staging (Ia/Ib)
Laparotomy group	38	42.66±7.25	1.67±0.39	22/16
Laparoscopy group	38	42.83±7.13	1.63±0.42	21/17
χ^2 / t		0.111	1.102	0.054
P		0.912	0.274	0.817

1.1 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria: (1) Endometrial carcinoma was clearly diagnosed by pathological examination before operation; (2) FIGO staging was in stage I; (3) Muscular layer invasion was found to be less than 1/2 by imaging examination, and lymph node metastasis was not found; (4) All patients were diagnosed for the first time and did not undergo radiotherapy and chemotherapy; (5) Patients' clinical data were complete; (6) All were approved by the hospital ethics committee (Approval number: 2021-255-001).

Exclusion criteria: (1) Patients who could not undergo surgical treatment due to chronic underlying diseases; (2) Patients who were in the acute attack stage of infectious diseases and inflammation; (3) Patients with conscious dysfunction; (4) Sufferers who had the history of abdominal operation; (5) Sufferers with advanced endometrial cancer; (6) Patients with sexual dysfunction.

Methods

The sufferers in the laparotomy one were treated by traditional laparotomy. The head low hip high bladder lithotomy position was taken, and general anesthesia was given with tracheal intubation. An incision was made at the center or left side of the patients' lower abdomen with a length of about 15 cm. After entering the abdomen, routine exploration was performed, and 100 mL of pelvic fluid was collected and sent for cytological examination. Uterus was excised conventionally and lymph node dissection were performed, and then the incision was sutured layer by layer, and drainage strips were placed. The sufferers in the laparoscopy one were treated with laparoscopic surgery, and the pelvic and abdominal cavity tissues were explored by the "four-hole method", and then 100 mL of pelvic fluid was collected and sent for cytological examination. The fallopian tubes were ligated with silk thread, and the right pelvic peritoneum was opened along the psoas major muscle. The ovarian blood vessels were ligated at the level of the patients' common iliac vessels with No. 4 silk thread, and then the tread was cut off. The bilateral round ligaments and pelvic

infundibulum ligaments were electrocuted to open the ligaments and peritoneal reentry of bladder. Then the lymph nodes were dissected and the bleeding was stopped by electrocoagulation, and after the vaginal stump was sutured and rinsed, a drainage tube was placed, and the incision was closed.

Observation indicators

(1) Perioperative indicators: The surgery duration, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative exhaust duration, and hospital stay were recorded and compared. (2) Sexual function: Before operation and six months after surgery, the sexual function of the 2 groups was evaluated according to the International Brief Index Scale of Sexual Functioning for Women (BISF-W), including sexual arousal, sexual desire, orgasm and abnormal symptoms in sexual behavior. The greater the point, the better the sexual function. (3) Nutritional status: The fasting elbow venous blood were collected of the two groups was collected in the morning before operation and 3 days after operation, centrifuged at a speed of $3000r \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ (centrifugal radius: 13cm) for 10 minutes, and then the upper layer serum was collected to detect the content of total protein (TP), albumin (ALB) and prealbumin (PAB) in the serum of the 2 groups by an automatic biochemical analyzer (provided by Shandong Gaoxin Biosensor Research Institute Co., Ltd.). (4) Inflammatory reaction: The serum C-reactive protein (CRP), tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) levels in the 2 groups were measured by ELISA method before operation and 3 days after operation. The ELISA kit was provided by Shanghai Unionwell Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (5) Complications: The incidence of complications was recorded and compared between the 2 groups.

Statistical methods

SPSS 21.0 was used for data analysis. The count data were represented in the form of n (%), and pairwise comparison was conducted with χ^2 -test; measurement data conformed to normal distribution and homogeneity of variance were represented in the form of ($\bar{x} \pm s$), and pairwise comparison was conducted with independent sample *t*-test. $P < 0.05$ meant the distinction was obvious.

RESULTS

Perioperative indicators

Compare to the laparotomy one, the surgery duration, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative exhaust duration, and hospital stay in the laparoscopy one were obviously decreased ($P < 0.05$). It had no obvious distinction in dissected lymph node number between the 2 groups ($P > 0.05$). See Table 2 and Figure 1.

Table 2 The perioperative indicators compared between the 2 groups ($\bar{x} \pm s$)

Group	n	Operation time (min)	Intraoperative blood loss (mL)	Postoperative exhaust time (h)	Hospital stay (d)	Dissected lymph node number (Pieces)
Laparotomy group	38	199.28±18.37	372.74±24.30	50.67±6.12	12.71±2.30	25.07±8.82

Laparos copy group	38	158.42±14.0	192.57±19.1	32.58±4.99	10.25±2.22	25.42±8.27
<i>t</i>		10.895	35.884	14.052	4.705	0.148
<i>P</i>		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.883

Figure 1 The perioperative related indicators compared between the 2 groups

Note: **** indicates $P < 0.0001$

Sexual function

The scores of sexual arousal, libido, orgasm, and abnormal symptoms in sexual behavior in the laparoscopy group after surgery had no significant difference compared with those before operation ($P < 0.05$); the points of all dimensions in the laparotomy one were obviously reduced in comparison of the one before operation ($P < 0.05$); and the points of sexual function in the laparoscopy one after surgery were greater than the one in the laparotomy one ($P < 0.05$). See Table 3 and Figure 2.

Table 3 The sexual function points compared between the 2 groups ($\bar{x} \pm s$)

Group	Time	Sexual arousal	Sexual desire	Orgasm	Abnormal symptoms in sexual behavior
Laparotomy group (n=38)	Before surgery	152.47±22.5 8	161.46±21.5 8	161.49±21.3 0	161.47±23.3 0
	After surgery	131.46±21.7 5 ^a	144.52±22.3 9 ^a	143.38±20.5 4 ^a	141.96±20.7 9 ^a
Laparoscopy group (n=38)	Before surgery	152.13±22.4 4	161.44±21.2 9	161.36±21.7 6	161.13±22.7 6
	After surgery	151.48±22.3 ^b	160.46±21.4 ^b	160.49±20.4 ^b	160.45±19.8 ^b

Note: Compare to the one before surgery, ^a indicates $P < 0.05$; compare to postoperative laparotomy one, ^b indicates $P < 0.05$

Figure 2 The postoperative sexual function scores compared between the 2 groups

Note: ** indicates $P < 0.001$; *** indicates $P < 0.001$

2.3 Nutritional status

The postoperative serum TP, ALB and PAB levels in the 2 groups were obviously reduced compared with the one before operation ($P < 0.05$); the postoperative serum TP, ALB and PAB levels in the laparoscopy one were obviously greater than the laparotomy one ($P < 0.05$). See Table 4 and Figure 3.

Table 4 The nutritional indicators compared between the 2 groups

Group	Time	TP (g/L)	ALB (g/L)	PAB (mg/L)
Laparotomy group (n=38)	Before surgery	68.34±2.52	41.85±4.30	242.14±17.07
	After surgery	51.54±4.73 ^a	27.42±5.73 ^a	180.07±18.36 ^a
Laparoscopy group (n=38)	Before surgery	68.30±2.49	41.70±4.18	242.09±17.94
	After surgery	62.39± 3.47 ^{ab}	33.07± 5.84 ^{ab}	213.10± 19.85 ^{ab}

Note: Compare to the one before surgery, ^a indicates $P < 0.05$; compare to postoperative laparotomy one, ^b indicates $P < 0.05$

Figure 3 The postoperative nutritional indicators compared between the 2 groups
 Note: *** indicates $P < 0.001$; **** indicates $P < 0.0001$

Inflammatory response

The postoperative serum CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6 levels in the 2 groups were significantly increased compared with the one before operation ($P < 0.05$); and the postoperative serum CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6 levels in the laparoscopy one were obviously reduced compared with the laparotomy one ($P < 0.05$). See Table 5 and Figure 4.

Table 5 The inflammatory factor levels compared between the 2 groups

Group	Time	CRP (mg/L)	TNF- α (ng/L)	IL-6 (ng/L)
Laparotomy group (n=38)	Before surgery	6.03 $\pm$ 1.82	13.48 $\pm$ 2.09	2.80 $\pm$ 1.16
	After surgery	22.69 $\pm$ 4.07 ^a	20.10 $\pm$ 2.52 ^a	7.42 $\pm$ 1.53 ^a
Laparoscopy group (n=38)	Before surgery	6.12 $\pm$ 1.85	13.52 $\pm$ 2.15	2.82 $\pm$ 1.18
	After surgery	13.85 $\pm$ 2.83 ^{ab}	15.46 $\pm$ 2.28 ^{ab}	4.14 $\pm$ 1.47 ^{ab}

Note: Compared with those before surgery, ^a indicates $P < 0.05$; compare to postoperative laparotomy one, ^b indicates $P < 0.05$

Figure 4 The postoperative inflammatory factor levels compared between the 2 groups

Note: **** indicates $P < 0.0001$

Complications

The total frequency of complications in the laparoscopy one was 13.16% (5/38), and that in the laparotomy group was 34.191 % (13/38). In comparison of the laparotomy one, the total frequency of complications in the laparoscopy one was obviously reduced ($P < 0.05$). See Table 6.

Table 6 The frequency of complications compared between the 2 groups [n (%)]

Complications	Laparotomy group (n=38)	Laparoscopy group (n=38)
Ureter injury	1 (2.63)	1 (2.63)
Intestinal damage	1 (2.63)	0 (0)
Incision infection	3 (7.89)	1 (2.63)
Lower extremity venous thrombosis	1 (2.63)	0 (0)
Urinary retention	3 (7.89)	1 (2.63)

Rectal dysfunction	2 (5.26)	1 (2.63)
Bladder dysfunction	2 (5.26)	1 (2.63)
Total incidence	13 (34.19)	5 (13.16)
χ^2	4.659	
<i>P</i>	0.031	

DISCUSSION

Endometrial cancer is highly occult and patients usually have no clinical symptoms in the early stage. As the disease progresses, symptoms such as irregular vaginal bleeding and increased vaginal secretions gradually occur. If secondary infection occurs, purulent and foul-smelling secretions may appear. When the disease progresses to an advanced stage, symptoms such as anemia, weight loss, and pain may occur [14-16]. Most of the pathological types of endometrial carcinoma are adenocarcinoma, and these patients are less sensitive to radiotherapy. Surgery is the main means for the therapy of sufferers with early endometrial carcinoma. If necessary, radiotherapy, chemotherapy or hormone therapy is supplemented, and most patients can obtain an ideal prognosis [17-18]. Traditional laparotomy can directly resect the tumor tissues and surrounding tissues, but the massive blood loss during the operation and the long operation time may cause postoperative inflammatory response and decline in nutritional status, which may cause adversely affects to the postoperative recovery of patients [19-20]. With the continuous development of medical technology, laparoscopic technology has gradually been widely used in the clinical therapy of endometrial cancer [21]. Laparoscopic surgery is a minimally invasive procedure that does not require large-scale direct exposure of the patients' abdominal cavity and pelvic cavity. It has high surgical accuracy and can reduce the scope of surgical resection; it can also reduce the degree of damage to blood vessels and reduce intraoperative blood loss [22].

This study found that the surgery duration, intraoperative blood loss, postoperative exhaust duration, hospitalization time and the incidence of complications in the laparoscopy one were obviously reduced in comparison of the one in the laparotomy one ($P < 0.05$), but it had no obvious distinction in the dissected lymph node number between the 2 groups ($P > 0.05$). It is suggested that laparoscopic operation could effectively shorten the surgery duration and decrease intraoperative blood loss in sufferers with endometrial cancer, achieve the same lymph node dissection effects as traditional laparotomy, and cause less damage to the patients' bodies, which is conducive to reducing the risk of postoperative complications and promoting their recovery. This is because laparoscopy can magnify the field of view and clearly show the tissue structure of the patients' lesions. In addition, the operator's fine and skillful operation can prevent the surrounding tissue damage and shorten the operation time, thereby improving the degree of body trauma; the pneumoperitoneum expansion effect used during the operation can cause compression on the blood vessels, and the surgical incision is less, which is conducive to reducing the amount of blood loss during the surgery. In addition, the operation is performed in a closed space, which could effectively decrease the damage to the

abdominal organs of the patients, help to accelerate the recovery of the patients' gastrointestinal functions, enhance immunity, and reduce the risk of complications.

Hysterectomy can cause damage to the uterine ligament and pelvic floor structure of the patients, and also damage the plexus uterovaginalis, reduce the lubrication of the cervix, cause the patients' vagina to be shortened and dry, and then bring adversely effects the patients' sexual life after surgery [23-24]. In addition, the ratio of dopamine and dethyroid hormone in the body may be changed after operation, and the patients have negative emotions, which also affects patients' sexual function [25-26]. This research found that it had no obvious distinction in the scores of sexual arousal, sexual desire, orgasm, and abnormal symptoms in sexual behavior in the laparoscopy group after surgery compared with those before operation ($P > 0.05$); the points of each dimension in the laparotomy one were obviously reduced in comparison of the one before surgery ($P < 0.05$); and the various points of sexual function in the laparoscopy one after operation were greater than the laparotomy one ($P < 0.05$). It shows that laparoscopic surgery has a certain protective impact on sexual function in sufferers with endometrial carcinoma. The reasons are that laparoscopic surgery has a high degree of precision, which can clearly show the anatomical level, reduce the damage to the vagina and protect the integrity of the pelvic cavity to the greatest extent. It can prevent vaginal discomfort and pain at the top of the vagina during sexual intercourse, and is beneficial to the recovery of postoperative sexual function.

Most cancer patients usually suffer from malnutrition and poor immune function, which can lead to increased risk of complications and mortality, and bring adversely effects on the prognosis of patients [27]. TP, ALB and PAB can reflect the nutritional status of the sufferers' bodies [28]. This research finding that the postoperative serum TP, ALB and PAB levels in the 2 groups were obviously reduced compared with the one before operation ($P < 0.05$); and the postoperative serum TP, ALB and PAB levels in the laparoscopy one were obviously greater than the one in the laparotomy one ($P < 0.05$). It is suggested that laparoscopic surgery could have the improvement on the postoperative immune function of sufferers with endometrial cancer, and has a positive impact on promoting postoperative recovery. This is because the surgical procedure has less trauma to the body, and the patients' abdominal cavity and pelvic cavity are not exposed to a large area during the operation, which has less impact on gastrointestinal function. Surgery is a traumatic operation, which can induce the body's inflammatory response, which in turn aggravates physiological dysfunction and may lead to an increase in the incidence of postoperative complications in patients [29]. Surgical trauma can greatly increase the content of inflammatory factors such as CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6 that aggravates the degree of inflammatory response in the body, which is not conducive to postoperative recovery of sufferers [30]. This research found that postoperative serum CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6 levels in the 2 groups were significantly increased in comparison of the one before operation ($P < 0.05$); however, postoperative serum CRP, TNF- α , and IL-6 levels in the laparoscopy one were obviously reduced compared with the one in the laparotomy one ($P < 0.05$). It shows that the degree of inflammatory response in patients with endometrial cancer

after laparoscopic surgery is lighter. The reasons are that the surgical incision and resection range of this surgical method are less, the amount of intraoperative blood loss of patients is less, and the degree of inflammatory response is lighter.

All in all, laparoscopic surgery treating patients with early endometrial cancer is less traumatic and has a definite curative effect. It can achieve the same effects of lymph node dissection as traditional laparotomy, could effectively reduce the occurrence of postoperative complications, and has a certain protective impact on sexual function. And the degree of postoperative inflammatory reaction is lighter and the nutritional status of patients is more ideal. However, the restrictions of this research are also obvious, the number of instances included is small and the source is single, and the research energy is limited, so further research is needed.

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